

Papyrus Amherst 63

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Entry tags: Aramaic Religions, Text, Jewish Traditions, Religious Group, Early Jewish Literature, Ancient Egyptian Text

Papyrus Amherst 63, also known as the "Mystery Papyrus," has been an enigma for quite some time. It is a large text, with a total of 23 columns. The text is also diverse in its content. There are not any prohibitions or legal literature in this corpus. It seems to be a collection of literature – prayers, poems, hymns, psalms, blessings, and it concludes with a literary tale about the seventh-century revolt of Shamash-shum-ukin of Babylonia against his brother, Assurbanipal of Assyria. There is a reference to the worship of various gods such as Mar, Anat, Bethel, Ba'al, and Adonai. There are hymns that are dedicated to the Jewish God YHWH or Adonai, the Babylonian goddess Nanay, and to various other Semitic deities. This collection of deities represents the religious ideologies of the Aramaic-speaking communities of the Babylonians, Syrians, and Jews, at the very least. The diversity incorporated in the text is only the beginning of its complexity. This document was purchased by Lord Amherst at the end of the 19th century and now resides in The Morgan Library in New York City. This papyrus' provenance is ancient Egypt. It was found in a jar outside of Thebes but is thought by some to originate around Elephantine and Aswan. Considering it was written in Egypt, it is not surprising that the script is Demotic, the penultimate phase of the Egyptian language and in regular use for legal, economic texts, as well as correspondence and literature. Considering the various cultures that resided in Egypt, it is also not surprising that texts in the Aramaic language were produced. The most surprising thing about this papyrus is that it is written in Demotic script while the language is Aramaic. The context of production is relatively unknown. Some have suggested that it was produced in the context of the community. It is also possible that a professional scribe was hired to compose this text in the Demotic script. While this text has not received a great amount of attention there is one part of the content that drew a great deal of interest in the mid-1980s. It was discovered that col. XII 11-19 is a psalm that parallels Psalm 20 in the Hebrew Bible. This became a focal point of publications. Many articles written concerning this section look at the possibility of this text having the original version of the psalm. While that has been inconclusive, both this text and psalm 20 probably draw from the same original. This papyrus is still understudied and is starting to receive more attention from scholars.

Date Range: 399 BCE - 100 BCE

Region: Elephantine

Region tags: Egypt, Elephantine

Elephantine is an island west of Aswan in the Nile, downstream from the first cataract.

Status of Readership:

✓ Religious Specialists

Sources and Corpora

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: van der Toorn, Karel. Papyrus Amherst 63. Münster: Ugarit Verlag, 2018
- Source 2: Vleeming, Sven P, and Jan Wilhelmus Wesseliuss. Studies in Papyrus Amherst 63: Essays on the Aramaic Texts in Aramaic/Demotic Papyrus Amherst 63. Amsterdam: Juda Palache Instituut, 1985.
- Source 3: Holm, Tawny L. "Nanay and Her Lover: An Aramaic Sacred Marriage Text from Egypt." JNES 76.1 (2017): 1-37.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: https://www.academia.edu/44014332/Richard_C_Steiner_and_Charles_F_Nims_The_Aramaic_Text_in_Demotic_Script_Text_Translation_and_Notes_
- Source 1 Description: First complete edition of the entire text by Richard Steiner and Charles Nims

Online Corpora

Relevant online Primary Textual Corpora (original languages and/or translations)

- Source 1 URL: <https://www.themorgan.org/manuscript/318272>
- Source 1 Description: Website of the Morgan Library, which houses the manuscript.

General Variables

Materiality

Methods of Composition

– Written

↳ Inked

–with Ink

Medium upon which the text is written/incised

– Papyrus

Was the material modified before the writing or incising process?

– Physical preparation

Was the text modified before the writing or incising process?

–Other [specify]: N/A

Location

Is the text stored in a specific location?

[Note at which point in time, for reference, if known; select all that apply]

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The original place of storage and ritual use is unknown.

Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?

– Field doesn't know

Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?

– Field doesn't know

Production & Intended Audience

Production

Is the production of the text funded by the polity?

– No

Is the text considered official religious scripture?

– Field doesn't know

Written in distinctly religious/sacred language?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Being written in Demotic, it could represent the sacred language. However, this would really depend upon the time it was composed. That specific information is still unknown.

Intended Audience

What is the estimated number of people considered to be the audience of the text

This should be the total number of people who would serve as the intended audience for the text.

– Field doesn't know

Does the Religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members?

– Field doesn't know

Are there clear reformist movements?

(Reformism, as in not proselytizing to potential new conservative, but "conversion" - or rather, reform - to the "correct interpretation"?)

– No

Is the text in question employed in ritual practice?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There are religious texts, specifically Psalms, that could be used in ritual practice. However, there are no cultic texts or spells in the corpus.

Is there material significance to the text?

– I don't know

Context and Content of the Text (Beliefs and Practices)

Context

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– No

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Not that have been discovered

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– Field doesn't know

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

– Yes

↳ Cultural with religious implications?

– Yes

↳ Behavioral literature?

– Yes

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: Some religious texts included

Content

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary?
(Select all that apply)

–Other [specify]: Various Literature used in this particular community

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– No

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– No

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– I don't know

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– No

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– No

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dicated in the text?

– No

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

– No

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– No

Are formal burials present in the text?

– No

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– No

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– Yes

↳ A supreme high-god is present

– No

Notes: Various gods are present throughout the text. Various gods such as Mar, Anat, Bethel, Ba'al, Nabu, and Adonai are mentioned while the goddesses Marah and Nanay are also present. YHWH is referenced but there is disagreement about how to translate the title used for this deity.

Previously human spirits are present

– No

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings can be seen

– No

↳ Supernatural beings can be physically felt

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world

– Yes

↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs

– Yes

↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region

– No

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region

– Yes

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region

– I don't know

↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)

– Yes

↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)

– I don't know

Notes: It is not clear that every diety mentioned is able to see in every private region.

↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)

– Yes

↳ Know basic character (personal essence)

– Yes

↳ Know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)

– Yes

↳ Have other knowledge of this world

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings can reward

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings can punish

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings communicate with the living according to the text?

– I don't know

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger

– No

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature

–Specify: N/A

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

– Yes

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model?

– No

↳ Organized hierarchically?

– No

↳ Power of beings is domain specific?

– No

↳ Other organization of pantheon?

–Specify: Pantheon is based upon the communities. There are references to Canaanite and Babylonian pantheons

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– No

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– No

Are other categories of beings present?

–Other [specify]: Divine beings generally conceived as gods

Does the text guide divination practices?

– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– No

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– Yes

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known?

– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife?

– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime?

– Yes

↳ Highly emphasized?

– No

↳ Consists of good luck?

– No

↳ Consists of political success or power?

– No

↳ Consists of success in battle?

– No

↳ Consists of peace or social stability?

– Yes

↳ Consists of healthy crops or good weather?

– Yes

↳ Consists of success on journeys?

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure?

– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure?

– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health?

– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success?

– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants?

– No

↳ Other?
– Specify: N/A

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?
– No

Is an eschatology present in the text?
– No

Norms & Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?
– No

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?
– No

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?
– Yes

↳ Honesty/trustworthiness/integrity
– No

↳ Courage (in battle)
– No

↳ Courage (generic)
– Yes

↳ Compassion/empathy/kindness/benevolence
– Yes

↳ Mercy/forgiveness/tolerance
– Yes

↳ Generosity/charity
– No

↳ Selflessness/selfless giving
– No

↳ Righteousness/moral rectitude
– Yes

↳ Ritual purity/ritual adherence/abstention from sources of impurity
– Yes

↳ Respectfulness/courtesy
– No

↳ Familial obedience/filial piety
– No

↳ Fidelity/loyalty
– Yes

↳ Cooperation

- No
- ↳ Independence/creativity/freedom
– No
- ↳ Moderation/frugality
– No
- ↳ Forbearance/fortitude/patience
– No
- ↳ Diligence/self-discipline/excellence
– No
- ↳ Assertiveness/decisiveness/confidence/initiative
– No
- ↳ Strength (physical)
– No
- ↳ Power/status/nobility
– No
- ↳ Humility/modesty
– No
- ↳ Contentment/serenity/equanimity
– No
- ↳ Joyfulness/enthusiasm/cheerfulness
– No
- ↳ Optimism/hope
– No
- ↳ Gratitude/thankfulness
– No
- ↳ Reverence/awe/wonder
– Yes
- ↳ Faith/belief/trust/devotion
– Yes
- ↳ Wisdom/understanding
– Yes
- ↳ Discernment/intelligence
– No
- ↳ Beauty/attractiveness
– Yes
- ↳ Cleanliness (physical)/orderliness
– No
- ↳ Other important virtues
– Yes

Advocacy of Practices

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require castration?

– No

Does the text require fasting?

– No

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– No

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– No

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– No

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– I don't know

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– No

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– No

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– Yes

↳ On average, how many participants gather in one location?
– Field doesn't know

↳ Interval of time between performances (in hours)
– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks?

– No

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks?

– No

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is there use of intoxicants?

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– No

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– No

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– Yes

↳ Drama?

– No

↳ Comedy?

– No

↳ Tragedy?

– No

↳ Epic entertainment?

– Yes

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– No

Institutions & Production Environment of Text

Society & Institutions

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

– Other

Notes: They would be a diasporic society

Are there specific elements of society that have controlled the reproduction of the text?

– Other

Are there specific elements of society involved with the destruction of the text?

– Other

Welfare

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

– No

Other forms of welfare?

– No

Education

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

– Field doesn't know

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

– No

Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

– Field doesn't know

Does the text restrict education to religious professionals?

– Field doesn't know

Does the text restrict education among religious professionals?

– Field doesn't know

Is education gendered according to the text?

– Field doesn't know

Is education gendered with respect to this text and larger textual tradition?

– Yes

Does the text specify teaching relationships or ratios? (i.e.: 1:20; 1:1)

– No

Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

– No

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– No

Bureaucracy

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– No

Public Works

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– No

Taxation

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– No

Warfare

Does the text mention warfare?

– No

Food Production

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– No

Bibliography

General References

Reference: S. P. Vleeming, J. W. Wesselijs. *Studies in Papyrus Amherst 63*. isbn: 9789071396014.

Reference: Karel van der Toorn. *Becoming Diaspora Jews*. Yale University Press. isbn: 9780300243512.

Reference: Karel Van Der Toorn. *Papyrus Amherst 63*. Ugarit Verlag. isbn: 9783868352580.